

'Going home' in typological perspective – Complementary material

Julia Nintemann

jnintemann@uni-bremen.de

5. Vielfaltslinguistik

14.05.2024, Graz

1. The sample

Africa

Language	Affiliation	Source
ɛHua	Kxa	Collins & Gruber (2014)
Balanta	Atlantic-Congo, Bak	Fudeman (1999)
Central Kanuri	Saharan	Hutchison (1981)
Emai	Atlantic-Congo, Edoid	Schaefer & Egbokhare (2017)
Fa d'Ambô	Creole, Portuguese-based	Hagemeijer et al. (2020)
Fon	Atlantic-Congo, Gbe	Delafosse (1894)
Hdi	Afro-Asiatic, Chadic	Frajzyngier (2002)
Ik	Kuliak	Schrock (2017)
Jamsay	Dogon	Heath (2008)
Koyra Chiini	Songhay	Heath (1999)
Lango	Nilotic	Noonan (1992)
Maba	Maban	Weiss (2009)
Ma'di	Central Sudanic	Blackings & Fabb (2003)
Nama	Khoe-Kwadi	Hagman (1974)
Sandawe	Khoisan	Eaton (2010)
Supyire	Atlantic-Congo, Senufo	Carlson (1994)
Swahili	Atlantic-Congo, Bantu	Brauner & Herms (1986), Almasi et al. (2014), [NEN]
Wandala	Afro-Asiatic, Chadic	Frajzyngier (2012)
Wolaytta	Ta-Ne-Omotiç	Wakasa (2008)
Zialo	Mande	Babaev (2010)

Americas

Language	Affiliation	Source
Aguaruna	Chicham	Overall (2017)
Cavineña	Pano-Tanacan	Guillaume (2008)
Central Alaskan Yupik	Eskimo-Aleut	Miyaoka (2014)
Crow	Siouan	Graczyk (2007)
Hualapai	Cochimi-Yuman	Watahomigie et al. (1982)
Hup	Naduhup	Epps (2008)

Itzá Maya	Mayan	Hofling (2000)
Kulina	Pano-Tacanan	Dienst (2014)
Kwaza	unclassified	van der Voort (2004)
Mapudungun	Araucanian	Smeets (2008)
Movima	Isolate	Haude (2006)
Norogachi Tarahumara	Uto-Aztecan	Villalpando-Quiñonez (2019)
Paunaka	Arawakan	Terhart (2024)
Paya Kuna	Chibchan	Forster (2011)
San Francisco del Mar Huave	Huavean	Kim (2008)
Slave	Athabaskan	Rice (1989)
Tlatepuzco Chinantec	Otomanguan, Chinantecan	Merrifield (2008)
Trió	Cariban	Carlin (2004)
Yauyos Quechua	Quechuan	Shimelman (2017)
Yurok	Algic	Garrett (2014), Robins (1958)

Asia

Language	Affiliation	
Baba Malay	Creole (Malay-based)	Lee (2022)
Bunaq	Timor-Alor-Pantar	Schapper (2022)
Chukchi	Chukotko-Kamchatkan	Dunn (1999)
Domari	Indo-European, Indo-Iranian	Matras (2012)
Hebrew	Afro-Asiatic, Semitic	Nataliya Levkovych, p.c.
Japanese	Japonic	Kayo Kobayashi, p.c.
Japhug	Sino-Tibetan, Burmo-Qiangic	Jacques (2021)
Kalamang	West Bomberai	Visser (2022)
Karbi	Sino-Tibetan, Kuki-Chin-Naga	Konnerth (2020)
Kharia	Austroasiatic, Mundaic	Peterson (2011)
Khmer	Austroasiatic, Khmeric	Haiman (2011)
Kolyma Yukaghir	Yukaghir	Maslova (2003)
Korean	Koreanic	Ihm et al. (2003), [KLB]
Limbu	Sino-Tibetan, Himalayish	van Driem (1987)
Mongolian	Mongolic-Khitian	Janhunen (2012)
Nivkh	Isolate	Gruzdeva et al. (2013); [BTI2000]
Palula	Indo-European, Indo-Iranian	Liljegren (2016)
Thai	Tai-Kadai, Daic	Smyth (2002)
Udihe	Tungusic	Nikolaeva & Tolskaya (2001)
Yakkha	Sino-Tibetan, Himalayish	Schackow (2015)

Europe

Language	Affiliation	
Albanian	Indo-European, Albanian	Newmark et al. (1982)
Armenian (Eastern)	Indo-European, Armenic	Dum-Tragut (2009)
Basque	isolate	Hualde & Ortiz de Urbina (2003)
Crimean Tatar	Turkic, Kipchak	Kavitskaya (2010)
Finnish	Uralic, Finnic	White (2006)
French	Indo-European, Romance	Booth (2010)
Georgian	Kartvelian	Hewitt (2005)
German	Indo-European, Germanic	own competence
Greek	Indo-European, Graeco-Phrygian	Holton et al. (2004), [LPP Greek]
Hungarian	Uralic, Hungaric	Stolz & Nintemann (2024), Törkenczy (2002)
Ingush	Nakh-Daghestanian, Chechen-Ingush	Nichols (2011)
Italian	Indo-European, Romance	Valeria Perchio, p.c.
Lezgian	Nakh-Daghestanian, Lezgitic	Haspelmath (1993)
Lithuanian	Indo-European, Balto-Slavic	Ambrasas et al. (1997)
Maltese	Afro-Asiatic, Semitic	Maike Vorholt, p.c.
Swedish	Indo-European, Germanic	own competence
Turkish	Turkic, Oghuz	Ketrez (2012), [TCL02]
Ukrainian	Indo-European, Slavic	Nataliya Levkovich, p.c.
Welsh	Indo-European-Celtic	Deborah Arbes, Lynne Davies, p.c.
West Greenlandic	Eskimo-Aleut	Kahn & Valijärvi (2021)

Oceania

Language	Affiliation	
Abau	Sepik	Lock (2011)
Bardi	Nyunyulan	Bowern (2012)
Bislama	Creole, English-based	Crowley (2004)
Coastal Marind	Anim	Olsson (2021)
Duna	Isolate	San Roque (2008)
Garrwa	Garrwan	Mushin (2012)
Gooniyandi	Bunaban	McGregor (1990)
Gurindji	Pama-Nyungan, Desert Nyungic	Meakins & McConvell (2021)
Imonda	Border	Seiler (1985)
Komnzo	Yam	Döhler (2018)
Motuna	South Bougainville	Onishi (1994)

Neverver	Austronesian, Oceanic	Barbour (2012)
Ngardi	Pama-Nyungan, Desert Nyungic	Ennever (2021)
Nungon	Nuclear Trans New Guinea, Finisterre-Huon	Sarvasy (2017)
Rapanui	Austronesian, Oceanic	Kievit (2017)
Savosavo	Isolate	Wegener (2012)
Toqabaqita	Austronesian, Oceanic	Lichtenberk (2008)
Tulil	Taulil-Butam	Meng (2018)
Vaeakau-Taumako	Austronesian, Oceanic	Næss & Hovdhaugen (2011)
Wirangu	Pama-Nyungan, Thura-Yura	Hercus (1999)

2. Sources

- Almasi, Oswald, Michael D. Fallon & Nazish P. Wared. 2014. *Swahili Grammar for Introductory and Intermediate Levels: Sarufi ya Kiswahili cha Ngazi ya Kwanza na Kati*. Lanham: University Press of America.
- Ambrazas, Vytautas, Emma Geniušienė, Aleksas Girdenis, Nijolė Sližienė, Dalija Tekorienė, Adelė Valeckienė & Elena Valiulytė. 1997. *Lithuanian grammar*. Vilnius: Baltos Lankos.
- Babaev, Kirill. 2010. *Zialo: The newly-discovered Mande language of Guinea*. Munich: LINCOM.
- Barbour, Julie. 2012. *A grammar of Neverver* (Mouton Grammar Library 60). Berlin, Boston: De Gruyter Mouton.
- Blackings, Mairi J. & Nigel Fabb. 2003. *A Grammar of Ma'di* (Mouton Grammar Library 32). Berlin, New York: De Gruyter Mouton.
- Booth, Trudie M. 2010. *A complete French grammar for reference and practice*. Lanham: University Press of America.
- Bowern, Claire. 2012. *A grammar of Bardi* (Mouton Grammar Library 57). Berlin, Boston: De Gruyter Mouton.
- Brauner, Siegmund & Irmtraud Herms. 1986. *Lehrbuch des modernen Swahili*. Leipzig: Enzyklopädie.
- Carlin, Eithne B. 2004. *A grammar of Trio: A Cariban language of Suriname* (Duisburger Arbeiten zur Sprach- und Kulturwissenschaft 55). Frankfurt am Main: Peter Lang.
- Carlson, Robert. 1994. *A grammar of Supyire* (Mouton Grammar Library). Berlin, New York: De Gruyter Mouton.
- Collins, Chris & Jeffrey S. Gruber. 2014. *A grammar of ꞤHõã* (Quellen zur Khoisan-Forschung / Research in Khoisan Studies 32). Köln: Rüdiger Köppe Verlag.
- Crowley, Terry. 2004. *Bislama reference grammar* (Oceanic linguistics special publication 31). Honolulu: University of Hawai'i Press.
- Delafosse, Maurice. 1894. *Manuel Dahoméen: Grammaire – Chrestomathie dictionnaire Français-Dahoméen et Dahoméen-Français*. Paris: Ernest Leroux.
- Dienst, Stefan. 2014. *A grammar of Kulina* (Mouton Grammar Library 66). Berlin, Boston: De Gruyter Mouton.
- Döhler, Christian. 2018. *A grammar of Komnzo* (Studies in Diversity Linguistics 22). Berlin: Language Science Press.
- Dum-Tragut, Jasmine. 2009. *Armenian: Modern Eastern Armenian* (London Oriental and African language library 14). Amsterdam: Benjamins.
- Dunn, Michael J. 1999. *A Grammar of Chukchi*. Canberra: Australian National University dissertation.
- Eaton, Helen. 2010. *A Sandawe grammar*. Dallas: SIL.
- Ennever, Thomas. 2021. *A grammar of Ngardi: As spoken by Freda Tjama, Margaret Yinjuru Bumblebee, Dora Mungkirna Rockman, Peggy Yalurrngali Rockman, Yunuja Nampijin, Dampa*

- Yujuyu Nampijin, Maudie Mandigalli, Kathleen Padoon, Payi Payi Napangardi, Patricia Lee, Nyirringawurru Japaljarri, Mark Moora, Marie Mudgedell and Patrick Smith.* Berlin, Boston: De Gruyter.
- Epps, Patience. 2008. *A grammar of Hup* (Mouton Grammar Library 43). Berlin, New York: Mouton de Gruyter.
- Forster, D. K. 2011. *Paya Kuna: An introductory grammar* (SIL Language and Culture Documentation and Description 14). Dallas: SIL.
- Frajzyngier, Zygmunt. 2002. *A grammar of Hdi* (Mouton Grammar Library). Berlin, New York: Mouton de Gruyter.
- Frajzyngier, Zygmunt. 2012. *A grammar of Wandala* (Mouton Grammar Library 47). Berlin, Boston: Mouton de Gruyter.
- Fudeman, Kirsten A. 1999. *Topics in the morphology and syntax of Balanta, an Atlantic language of Senegal*. Ithaca: Cornell University dissertation.
- Garrett, Andrew. 2014. *Basic Yurok* (Survey of California and Other Indian Languages, Report 16). Berkeley: Department of Linguistics, University of California Berkeley.
- Graczyk, Randolph. 2007. *A grammar of Crow: Apsáalooke Aliláau*. Lincoln: University of Nebraska Press.
- Gruzdeva, Ekaterina, Vladimir P. Nedjalkov & Galina A. Otaina (eds.). 2013. *A syntax of the Nivkh language: The Amur dialect* (Studies in Language Companion Series 139). Amsterdam: Benjamins.
- Guillaume, Antoine. 2008. *A grammar of Cavineña* (Mouton Grammar Library 44). Berlin, New York: Mouton de Gruyter.
- Hagemeyer, Tjerk, Philippe Maurer-Cecchini & Armando Zamora Segorbe. 2020. *A grammar of Fa d'Ambô* (Mouton Grammar Library 81). Berlin, Boston: De Gruyter.
- Hagman, Roy S. 1974. *Nama Hottetot grammar*. New York: Columbia University.
- Haiman, John. 2011. *Cambodian: Khmer* (London Oriental and African language library 16). Amsterdam: Benjamins.
- Haspelmath, Martin. 1993. *A grammar of Lezgian* (Mouton Grammar Library 9). Berlin, New York: Mouton de Gruyter.
- Haude, Katharina. 2006. *A grammar of Movima*. Nijmegen: Radboud University Nijmegen dissertation.
- Heath, Jeffrey. 1999. *A Grammar of Koyra Chiini: The Songhay of Timbuktu* (Mouton Grammar Library) (Mouton Grammar Library 19). Berlin, New York: De Gruyter Mouton.
- Heath, Jeffrey. 2008. *A grammar of Jamsay* (Mouton Grammar Library 45). Berlin, New York: De Gruyter Mouton.
- Hercus, Luise A. 1999. *A grammar of the Wirangu language from the west coast of South Australia* (Pacific linguistics: Series C 150). Canberra: The Australian National University.
- Hewitt, Brian G. 2005. *Georgian: A learner's grammar*, 2nd edn. (Essential grammars). London: Routledge.
- Hofling, Charles A. 2000. *Itzaj Maya Grammar*. Salt Lake City: University of Utah Press.
- Holton, David, Peter A. Mackridge & Irene Philippaki-Warbuton. 2004. *Greek: An essential grammar of the modern language*. London: Routledge.
- Hualde, Josê I. & Jon Ortiz de Urbina. 2003. *A grammar of Basque* (Mouton Grammar Library 26). Berlin, New York: De Gruyter Mouton.
- Hutchison, John P. 1981. *The Kanuri language: A reference grammar*. Madison: African Studies Program, University of Wisconsin.
- Ihm, Ho b., Kyung P. Hong & Suk in Chang. 2003. *Korean grammar for international learners*. Seoul: Yonsei University Press.
- Jacques, Guillaume. 2021. *A grammar of Japhug*. Berlin: Language Science Press.
- Janhunen, Juha A. 2012. *Mongolian* (London Oriental and African language library 19). Amsterdam, Philadelphia: John Benjamins.
- Kahn, Lily & Riitta-Liisa Valijärvi. 2021. *West Greenlandic*. London: Routledge.
- Kavitskaya, Darya. 2010. *Crimean Tatar*. München: LINCOM.
- Ketrez, F. N. 2012. *A student grammar of Turkish*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.

- Kievit, Paulus. 2017. *Grammar of RapNui* (Studies in Diversity Linguistics 12). Berlin: Language Science Press.
- Kim, Yuni. 2008. *Topics in the Phonology and Morphology of San Fransisco del Mar Huave*. Berkeley: University of California dissertation.
- Konnerth, Linda. 2020. *A grammar of Karbi*. Berlin, Boston: De Gruyter.
- Lee, Nala H. 2022. *A grammar of Modern Baba Malay*. Berlin, Boston: De Gruyter.
- Lichtenberk, Frantisek. 2008. *A grammar of Toqabaqita* (Mouton Grammar Library 42-1). Berlin: Mouton de Gruyter.
- Liljegren, Henrik. 2016. *A grammar of Palula* (Studies in Diversity Linguistics 8). Berlin: Language Science Press.
- Lock, Arnold H. 2011. *Abau grammar* (Data papers on Papua New Guinea languages 57). Ukarumpa: SIL-PNG.
- Maslova, Elena. 2003. *A grammar of Kolyma Yukaghir* (Mouton Grammar Library 27). Berlin, New York: Walter de Gruyter.
- Matras, Yaron. 2012. *A grammar of Domari* (Mouton Grammar Library 59). Berlin, Boston: De Gruyter Mouton.
- McGregor, William B. 1990. *A functional grammar of Gooniyandi* (Studies in Language Companion Series 22). Amsterdam, Philadelphia: John Benjamins Publishing Company.
- Meakins, Felicity & Patrick McConvell. 2021. *A grammar of Gurindji: As spoken by Violet Wadrill, Ronnie Wavehill, Dandy Danbayarri, Biddy Wavehill, Topsy Dodd Ngarnjal, Long Johnny Kijngayarri, Banjo Ryan, Pincher Nyurmiari and Blanche Bulngari* (Mouton Grammar Library 91). Berlin, Boston: De Gruyter.
- Meng, Chenxi. 2018. *A grammar of Tulil*. Victoria: La Trobe University dissertation.
- Merrifield, William R. 2008. *The Tlatepuzco Chinantec language*. Unpublished manuscript.
- Miyaoka, Osahito. 2014. *A grammar of Central Alaskan Yupik (CAY)* (Mouton Grammar Library 58). Berlin, Boston: De Gruyter Mouton.
- Mushin, Ilana. 2012. *A grammar of (Western) Garrwa* (Pacific linguistics 637). Boston MA: De Gruyter Mouton.
- Næss, Åshild & Even Hovdhaugen. 2011. *A grammar of Vaeakau-Taumako* (Mouton Grammar Library 52). Berlin, Boston: De Gruyter Mouton.
- Newmark, Leonard, Philip Hubbard & Peter Prifti. 1982. *Standard Albanian: A reference grammar for students*. Stanford: Stanford University Press.
- Nichols, Johanna. 2011. *Ingush grammar* (University of California publications 143). Berkeley CA: University of California Press.
- Nikolaeva, Irina & Maria Tolskaya. 2001. *A grammar of Udihe*. Berlin, New York: Mouton de Gruyter.
- Noonan, Michael. 1992. *A grammar of Lango* (Mouton Grammar Library 7). Berlin: De Gruyter Mouton.
- Olsson, Bruno. 2021. *A grammar of Coastal Marind*. Berlin, Boston: De Gruyter.
- Onishi, Masayuki. 1994. *A grammar of Motuna (Bougainville, Papua New Guinea)*. Canberra: The Australian National University.
- Overall, Simon E. 2017. *A grammar of Aguaruna (liniá Chicham)* (Mouton Grammar Library 68). Berlin, Boston: De Gruyter Mouton.
- Peterson, John. 2011. *A grammar of Kharia: A South Munda language*. Leiden, Boston: Brill.
- Rice, Keren. 1989. *A grammar of Slave* (Mouton Grammar Library 5). Berlin, New York: De Gruyter Mouton.
- Robins, R. H. 1958. *The Yurok language: Grammar, texts, lexicon*. Berkeley, Los Angeles: University of California Press.
- San Roque, Lila. 2008. *An introduction to Duna grammar*. Canberra: The Australian National University dissertation.
- Sarvasy, Hannah S. 2017. *A grammar of Nungon: A Papuan language of Northeast New Guinea* (Grammars and language sketches of the world's languages 2). Leiden, Boston: Brill.
- Schackow, Diana. 2015. *A grammar of Yakkha* (Studies in Diversity Linguistics 7). Berlin: Language Science Press.

- Schaefer, Ronald P. & Francis O. Egbokhare. 2017. *A grammar of Emai* (Mouton Grammar Library 72). Berlin, Boston: De Gruyter Mouton.
- Schapper, Antoinette. 2022. *A grammar of Bunaq*. Berlin, Boston: De Gruyter.
- Schrock, Terrill B. 2017. *The Ik language: Dictionary and grammar sketch* (African Language Grammars and Dictionaries 1). Berlin: Language Science Press.
- Seiler, Walter. 1985. *Imonda, a Papuan language*. Canberra: Research School of Pacific and Asian Studies, Australian National University.
- Shimelman, Aviva. 2017. *A grammar of Yauyos Quechua*. Berlin: Language Science Press.
- Smeets, Ineke. 2008. *A grammar of Mapuche* (Mouton Grammar Library 41). Berlin, New York: De Gruyter Mouton.
- Smyth, David. 2002. *Thai: An essential grammar* (Routledge essential grammars). London, New York: Routledge.
- Stolz, Thomas & Julia Nintemann. 2024. *Special Onymic Grammar in typological perspective: Cross-linguistic data, recurrent patterns, functional explanations* (Studia Typologica 34). Berlin, Boston: De Gruyter Mouton.
- Terhart, Lena. 2024. *A grammar of Paunaka*. Berlin: Language Science Press.
- Törkenczy, Miklós. 2002. *Practical Hungarian grammar*. Budapest: Corvina.
- van der Voort, Hein. 2004. *A grammar of Kwaza* (Mouton Grammar Library 29). Berlin, New York: Mouton de Gruyter.
- van Driem, George. 1987. *A grammar of Limbu* (Mouton Grammar Library 4). Berlin: Mouton de Gruyter.
- Villalpando-Quiñonez, Jesús. 2019. *Grammatical aspect in Norogachi Rarámuri (Tarahumara; Uto-Aztecan)*. Denver: University of Colorado at Boulder dissertation.
- Visser, Eline. 2022. *A grammar of Kalamang*. Berlin: Language Science Press.
- Wakasa, Motomichi. 2008. *A descriptive study of the modern Wolaytta language*. Tokyo: The University of Tokyo dissertation.
- Watahomigie, Lucille, Jorigine Bender & Akira Y. Yamamoto. 1982. *Hualapai reference grammar*. Los Angeles: American Indian Studies Center, UCLA.
- Wegener, Claudia. 2012. *A grammar of Savosavo* (Mouton Grammar Library 61). Berlin, Boston: De Gruyter Mouton.
- Weiss, Doris. 2009. *Phonologie et morphosyntaxe du maba*. Lyon: Université Lumière Lyon 2 dissertation.
- White, Leila. 2006. *A grammar book of Finnish*. Helsinki: Finn Lectura.

Bible translations

[NEN] = Neno: Biblia Takatifu © 1984, 1989, 2009, 2015 by Biblica, Inc.

[KLB] = Korean Living Bible (현대인의 성경) © 1985 by Biblica, Inc.

[BTI2000] = BTI. 2000. Рождество Иисуса Христа: Евангелие от Луки 2,1-20 на 80 языках народов СНГ. (The birth of Jesus Christ in 80 languages of the CIS). Moscow: Bible Translation Institute.

[TCL02] = Kutsal Kitap © The Bible Society in Turkey (Kitapı Mukaddes Şirketi), The Translation Trust / Yeni Yaşam Yayınları 2001, 2008.

Le Petit Prince translations

[LPP Greek] = Theodorakis, Thanasis K. (1993): Ο μικρός πρίγκιπας. O mikros prinkipas. Athens: Ekdosis Pella.

References

Haspelmath, Martin. 2019. Differential place marking and differential object marking. *STUF - Language Typology and Universals* 72(3). 313–334.

Abbreviations

1, 2, 3 = 1st, 2nd, 3rd person, 2|3 = 2nd or 3rd person, I, II = Genders I, II, A = actor, ALL = allative, APP = appositional mood, B = gender agreement marker, CL = noun class, COMM = common noun, CONS = consecutive marker, CT = concessive, CVtemp = temporal converb, D = gender agreement marker, DEF = definite, EMPH = emphasis, EXT = extended, GEN = genitive, IFR = inferential, IMN = imminent (future), IMPF = imperfective aspect, IND = indicative mood, LNK = linker, LOC = locative, M = masculine, NMLZ = nominalizing morpheme, NOM = nominative, NTRL = neutral orientation, PL = plural, POSS = possessive, PROX = proximal, PRS = present tense, PRSTV = presentative, REAL = realis mood, SFL = sentence filler (expletive), SG = singular, SUB = subject, TOPO = toponym, U = undergoer, UT = *utrum*, V = gender agreement marker, VEN = ventive, VERT = vertitive, WP = witnessed past tense